

Exploring environmental and distributional impacts of different transition pathways for healthier and sustainable diets: an economic modelling study

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Summary

Background The EAT–Lancet (EL) report made a convincing case that a transformative diet shift could yield substantial health benefits while helping to respect key planetary boundaries. Shifting to a more plant-based EL diet requires an unprecedented break from historic trends of rising meat consumption. By exogenously shifting diets, existing studies do not provide guidance on how to shift diets. In this study, we model specific policies that might achieve such a dietary shift and their potential economic, environmental, and distributional impacts.

Methods In this economic modelling study, we used MAGNET, a global computable general equilibrium model, to explore how diets might be shifted from the business-as-usual trend of increased meat consumption between 2025 and 2050. We defined a policy bundle of three types of context-specific interventions: (1) nudging and information to shift consumer decisions, (2) adjusting fiscal policies by removing taxes on encouraged foods and subsidies on discouraged ones, and (3) introducing new price signals, such as taxes on high-emission foods and subsidies for encouraged foods. To evaluate how choice of interventions affects economic, environmental, and distributional outcomes, we analysed interactions of combined interventions and compared the policy bundle to an exogenous shift to the EL diet.

Findings The EL diet recommendations cannot be reached by the policy bundle. While reducing overconsumption and underconsumption, the policy bundle left a big gap with EL diet recommendations (3 times the recommended intake for red meat, and only 80% of recommended fruit and vegetable intake, 50% for pulses and nuts). No single intervention from the policy bundle shifted all diet components in the desired direction. Decomposition of the policy bundle showed the importance of regional context. In low-income regions, taxes and subsidies accounted for the largest share in the diet shift. In other regions, nudging and information had a stronger effect than did subsidies. The exogenous EL diet scenario assumed a shift in diets beyond the range observed in empirical studies and produced a counterproductive feedback by reducing the affordability of the EL diet. GHG emissions from the primary sector (agriculture and fisheries) decreased more with the policy bundle (–4 GTon CO₂ equivalent), as GHG taxes provided incentives to reduce fossil-based inputs lacking in the consumer-focused exogenous EL diet scenario (–3 GTon CO₂ equivalent). The shift away from fossil-based inputs also led to an increase in agricultural land area (27 million ha) with the policy bundle, while the exogenous EL diet scenario resulted in a decrease in agricultural land (–35 million ha). Affordability for the average household decreased when exogenously shifting the EL diet (EL diet costs increased 26.1%, household income 0.2%), but it increased with the policy bundle as subsidies lowered EL diet costs (–4.4%) more than it lowered income (–2.0%). Affordability judged against daily wages worsened most when exogenously shifting the EL diet (27.7% of the workforce) and increased slightly with the policy bundle (24.8% of the workforce). Most of the affected workers were in encouraged primary sectors (fruit and vegetables, pulses and nuts, fish), but the negative effects extended to the non-food sectors with the exogenous EL diet.

Interpretation The interventions chosen to change diets matter for the shift that can be attained and for the direction and size of the environmental, affordability, and distributional impacts. Price incentives can be a more effective, scalable, and just way to shift diets than the often preferred shift in consumer decisions, which make the EL diet more costly. Part of the trade-offs could be addressed by expanding the policy bundle with interventions to lower prices of encouraged foods (productivity increase, food loss and waste reduction) or reduce GHG emissions of food and non-food production, and with regulation of agricultural land expansion to reduce pressure on biodiversity. Increased productivity in lower-income regions could address the effect of past limited access to food and non-food technologies driving an increased reliance on imports in all scenarios. If designed well, it could improve affordability by lowering prices while increasing wages. Stimulating imports might help moderate prices of encouraged foods in case of unsurmountable local production limitations or preference for investing in manufacturing and services. These additional interventions address price and income concerns but are likely insufficient to attain a global shift to the EL diet, as food consumption is determined by more than affordability and nutritional needs.

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Introduction

The EAT–Lancet (EL) report¹ made a convincing case that a transformative diet shift could yield substantial health benefits while helping to respect key planetary boundaries. Shifting diets can address both global health and environmental crises of which the dire consequences are becoming increasingly apparent. The proposed transformation entails a shift towards a more plant-based diet, increased productivity of food production, and a reduction in food loss and waste.¹ Policy makers can learn from past gains in productivity and reduction of food loss and waste, but challenges such as yield gaps persist. In contrast, shifting to a more plant-based diet requires an unprecedented break

from rising meat consumption as incomes rise, alongside strengthening increased fruit and vegetable consumption. This study focuses on how this break in household consumption patterns might be achieved.

Most studies assume consumers to adhere to the EAT–Lancet diet, highlighting potential benefits but not specifying required interventions.^{2–4} In this study, we model specific policies (nudging and information, taxes, and subsidies) that might achieve such a dietary shift compared with the business-as-usual (BAU) trend of increased meat consumption between 2025 and 2050. The interventions chosen to shift toward the EL diet affect the feasibility of the shift and its impact, which we assess in

Research in context

Evidence before this study

The existing evidence on potential gains of the EAT–Lancet (EL) diet is dominated by empirical studies using detailed intake data to compute health and environmental gains from shifting diets. The environmental gains are generally based on lifecycle assessment data that do not take changes in production, trade, or non-food production and consumption into account. Existing studies of affordability of healthy diets use current prices or omit changes in income from a diet shift, providing only a partial assessment. Existing economic modelling studies generally impose a healthy diet as an exogenous consumption shift and are predominantly agricultural models omitting economy-wide feedback.

Added value of this study

Our study is, to our knowledge, the first to explicitly compare economic, environmental, and affordability impacts of exogenous consumption shifts to a policy bundle in an economy-wide global model. While the policy bundle comprises context-specific interventions, they represent three generic types of policies making our findings more generally applicable: nudging and information, removing existing price distortions, and introducing new price distortions. Breaking down impacts of separate interventions and replicating food consumption from the policy bundle through an exogenous consumption shift provides new insight in how the choice of interventions matters for all three types of impacts considered in this study.

Implications of all the available evidence

Our findings show that the choice of intervention determines the extent to which the EL diet can be reached and thus the health gains that can be attained. Consumption shifts and price-based

interventions generate different economy-wide feedback loops generating different economic, environmental and affordability outcomes. Relying on shifting consumption with nudging and information makes EL diets less affordable as it lacks targeted signals to producers to redirect production decisions provided by taxes, which can also fund subsidies to lower EL diet costs. Looking beyond primary food production is key with any large-scale food system shift. Environmental gains are limited in all scenarios compared with agriculture-focused studies because of increased non-food production and consumption. Although greenhouse gas taxes are effective in reducing emissions, agricultural land use increases by biomass replacing fossil fuels and extensification of crop production. Shifting to a more plant-based diet increases the demand for agricultural labour in all scenarios making affordability of the EL diet for workers an increasing concern due to a persistent wage gap with non-agricultural sectors. Additional interventions are especially needed to improve availability of fruit and vegetables. These interventions should look beyond productivity and food loss and waste reductions to international trade in case of strong local production limitations. Any intervention needs to consider wage impacts and movement of workers from discouraged to encouraged sectors—the increasing number of workers not able to afford the EL diet are in sectors producing encouraged food. Attaining a just shift to a healthier and more sustainable food system requires not only better empirical foundations for shifting consumer decisions as food consumption is determined by more than affordability and nutritional needs. It also requires creative thinking on new interventions and sustained collective action to fundamentally change food systems.

Figure 1: Framework for deriving context-specific policy bundles for shifting diets in the MAGNET model

Organisation of the interventions follows the distinction in intervention theories on enabling choices (yellow boxes) and interventions that steer choices by decreasing prices (green boxes) or increasing prices (blue boxes). Dashed boxes at the right side provide scenario codes used in the text and describe the quantification of the scenarios used in the MAGNET model. The policy bundle (PB) comprises all interventions. By running the interventions separately, we can break down the total impact of the policy bundle into the contributions of its components. Combinations of interventions used in figures and the main text are: align fiscal policies—combining RTXS and RSUB; GHG taxes—GHG; primary sector GHG taxes used to subsidise encouraged food sectors—GHG and GHG_S. Two scenarios shift food consumption exogenously to provide insight in the different impacts of reaching the same food consumption as in the policy bundle (PB) through an exogenous shift to policy bundle diet (PB_E), or provide a link to the existing literature by an exogenous shift to EAT-Lancet diet (EED). Details on the scenario implementation are provided in the appendix (pp 26–34). GHG=greenhouse gas. *Subsidies on poultry are kept in lower-income regions where consumption is below EAT-Lancet diet recommendation.

terms of environment (greenhouse gas [GHG] emissions, agricultural land use), economic consequences (minimum cost of the EL diet, household income, wages), and affordability of the EL diet (relative to household food expenditures, share of workers unable to afford the EL diet). To evaluate how choice of interventions affects outcomes, we broke down the policy bundle into the contributions of interventions and compared the policy bundle to an exogenous shift to the EL and policy bundle diet.

Methods

Devising policy bundles to shift future diets

There is no silver-bullet policy as the EL diet shift aims for healthy and sustainability goals while making the transition just.⁵ The aims for health and sustainability both address externalities, such as correcting the failure of markets to account for health and environmental costs of current diets. The most effective point of intervention depends on the goal. Increasing consumption of fruit and vegetables and of pulses and nuts is most effective for reducing premature

mortality⁶ and diet-related health costs, implying a focus on behavioural change of domestic consumers. Using diet changes as an instrument to reduce food system GHG emissions, however, implies targeting ruminant producers.⁶ Given the global impact of GHG emissions, an intervention targeting domestic producers is counterproductive if production shifts to a less efficient production abroad. Highlighting the environmental impact of food might also be more effective at changing consumption than highlighting dietary health concerns.⁷

Lacking conclusive evidence on how to shift diets permanently and at population level,⁷ we developed a policy bundle to steer towards the EL diet, building on frameworks for behavioural change^{7,8} that grouped interventions by the extent to which they constrain behaviour. The context-specific interventions started from macro-economic drivers, which are known to affect diet choices (figure 1). Diet changes will not be instantaneous, and economic circumstances will change over the implementation period. Any intervention thus needs to be evaluated against this

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of key feedback loops in the economic model
 Highly simplified representation of key interactions between consumption and production of different commodities in the modelling of the scenarios. Dashed lines indicate monetary flows (prices and income), solid lines indicate flows of commodities (goods, services and production factors). Feedback loops via international trade and intermediate input use of commodities (eg, use of non-food commodities in the production of food commodities) are omitted. Market equilibrium (supply=demand) is achieved by price adjustments (marked in yellow). Nudging and information change food consumption decisions (marked in green). Non-food consumption also changes as consumers decide on food and non-food consumption simultaneously, taking commodity price and income changes into account. Changed food and non-food demand modify prices and production patterns, which in turn modify demand for factors used in production and thus factor prices. Changing factor prices change the household income, which is derived from supplying production factors, closing the feedback loop to the consumer. Price incentive scenarios affect the tax and subsidies (marked in blue) that create a price wedge between market and consumer or producer prices used in decision making, affecting all food and non-food production and consumption decision directly or indirectly.

backdrop. Even more so given the solid evidence on higher income driving diet changes captured by Engels' law (decreasing food expenditure shares) and Bennet's law (less staples and more fruit, vegetables and meat). We take population and sector-specific productivity drivers as given, assuming that a strong reduction in household income is not a desirable intervention to reduce meat consumption.

The least invasive intervention is to convince consumers to shift their behaviour towards the EL diet. For example, tweaking food environments to make healthier choices easier (nudging), or providing information through food-based dietary guidelines (information). The second group of interventions is changing price incentives in line with the EL diet—ie, increasing prices of discouraged foods and lowering prices of encouraged foods. This intervention builds on solid evidence that prices matter for production and consumption decisions, underpinning the price elasticities in applied economic models. The potential of price signals is also illustrated by a review of 1500 climate change policies, which showed that only price incentives had a consistent and strong impact on GHG emission reduction.⁹

Our policy bundle consisted of three main blocs (figure 1): (1) nudging and information, to shift the food choices of consumers to the EL diet without changing economic incentives, a preferred option as it is least restrictive; (2) aligning existing fiscal policies with the EL diet, by removing taxes on encouraged foods and removing subsidies on discouraged foods; (3) introducing taxes and subsidies to represent unaccounted costs of GHG emissions, with receipts from primary (agricultural and fishery) GHG taxes used to subsidise primary sectors producing encouraged foods (fruit and vegetables, pulses and nuts, and fish). These subsidies set the net GHG tax on primary sectors to zero in line with their current exemption from GHG taxes while addressing concerns on the affordability of food¹⁰ and aiming to reduce impacts on vulnerable households depending on primary production.

Economic modelling

Global computable general equilibrium (CGE) modelling can analyse economy-wide effects of diet shifts on consumption, production, trade, prices, and income. Global CGEs capture interactions across all sectors and regions, accounting for trade and market feedback while allowing for price-driven adjustments. Non-price mechanisms, such as consumer preference shifts, can also be incorporated. Market-clearing through price changes forms the core of CGE models, assuring that demand matches supply in all commodity and factor markets. It also creates interdependency between all production and consumption decisions illustrated in figure 2.

To illustrate the interdependencies, consider a shift in food consumption through nudging and information that reduces demand for food. The prices in the food market will go down, leading to lower food prices. As food producers receive less for their output, they reduce their demand for production factors (land, labour, capital) to avoid losses and food production decreases. Reduced demand for factors by the food sector will lower the price of factors, which lowers the production cost of both food and non-food sectors. This reduced price moderates the reduction of factor demand by the food sector, while stimulating production of the non-food sector by lowering their production costs. The consumer demands less food, which it can purchase at a

lower price, leaving more income to spend on non-food. This will increase demand for non-food, which may include the non-food use of the commodity (eg, as feed or fuel), moderating the reduced demand for food by consumers. The lower demand for factors, however, also lowers household income, which is based on factor payments by sectors. This decrease in income moderates the increased demand for non-food and thus the scope for the non-food sector to expand. These interrelated adjustments in the markets for food, non-food, and factors will continue until all markets are in equilibrium again with supply being equal to demand. Reducing food demand through increased consumption taxes will have a different effect. It could potentially reduce demand for non-food if the income share of food increases after the tax, setting in motion a different series of feedback loops in the global economic system.

We used MAGNET,¹¹ a global CGE model extended to better reflect land use and bio-economy dynamics. Three key extensions addressed the EL diet's context-specific effects, affordability, and environmental impact. The diet extension tracked food content changes in physical units, enabling regional variations in diet shifts. It relied on an endogenous variable tracing changes in the primary content of processed foods from changes in production and global trade flows.³ Affordability was assessed by calculating the minimum cost of the EL diet relative to household food expenditures and income, and as a share of daily wages. These wages varied by five types of workers and 77 sectors providing an endogenous distribution of labour income. Market segmentation captured the persistent gap between agricultural and non-agricultural wages.¹² MAGNET was extended to capture feedback on non-food bio-based sectors,¹³ which might reduce GHG emissions in the overall economy but offset environmental gains in the agricultural sector by increasing its GHG emissions and land use. Lower agricultural prices from reduced food demand can increase land use for biomass production used by non-food sectors. Similarly, reduced food spending can shift consumption to GHG-intensive non-food, partly mitigating emissions reductions.³ The appendix (pp 10–25) shows a description of the model and data sources used.

Scenario quantification

The scenarios were quantified combining the MAGNET database and external data (appendix pp 26–34). The BAU scenario was a combination of population and productivity shocks. Household consumption and the country-specific EL diet recommendations by food group were based on intake data² and excluded food loss and waste. In the exogenous shift to EL diet (EED) scenario, EL recommendations were used to fix consumption at food group level, allowing households' freedom to select the most preferred combination of food items in each group. The extent to which consumption could be shifted towards the EL diet using nudging and information (NI) was derived from literature.⁷ Evidence was limited in terms of products

(red meat, vegetables, and fruits), regional context (Northern America and Europe), population subgroup (students), interventions (mostly information), and only assessed short run impact. While we used the lowest estimates and adjust the shifts proportional to differences in intake (appendix p 27) the estimates remain optimistic for our global application to the general population. Daily red meat consumption reductions range from a 2.1 to 11.8 g across regions. Increases in fruit, vegetables, pulses and nuts range from 15.1 to 45.0 g.

Alignment of fiscal policy (AP scenario) removed existing taxes on foods to be consumed more and removed existing subsidies on foods to be consumed less, as captured in the GTAP database.¹⁴ The GHG scenario imposed a carbon price of US\$100/ton CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) on emissions of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O, based on a previous climate-focused study using an ensemble of global economic models, including MAGNET.¹⁵ From a polluter pays principle, agricultural sectors also need to pay for GHG emissions, being responsible for about a quarter of GHG emissions.¹⁶ Denmark recently announced plans to start pricing GHG emissions from livestock¹⁷ with \$40/ton CO₂e in 2030 and rising to around \$100/ton CO₂e in 2035. The latter corresponds with the imposed GHG price in this study. Primary sector GHG tax revenues were redistributed to encouraged sectors (fruit and vegetables, pulses and nuts, fish) to keep net GHG taxes on the primary sector at zero (GHG_S). The policy bundle scenario (PB) combines NI, alignment of fiscal policies, and GHG taxes with redistribution to encouraged sectors (GHG_S).

We also ran a scenario in which we set the diet from the policy bundle exogenous (PB_E). The extent of the diet shift was the same as under the policy bundle scenario (PB) but achieved through different means. It shed light on the impact of how the diets were shifted, which could not be as clearly seen from a comparison to the exogenous shift the EL diet (EED) scenario, which differed in both the level of the shift and means through which it was achieved. We conducted sensitivity analyses on the policy bundle scenario for price elasticities and GHG prices, including a scenario in which GHG prices varied by regional income (appendix pp 35–41).

See Online for appendix

Role of funding source

The funders of this study had no role in the model set-up and scenario design, nor in the data collection, data analysis, model result interpretation, or writing of the paper.

Results

By 2050, the PB improved consumption across food groups and regions compared with BAU developments, but substantial gaps with the EL recommendations remained (figure 3A). Fruit and vegetable intake remains at 80% of the recommended 500 g/capita per day and pulses and nuts at 50% of 75 g/capita per day. Global average consumption of fruit and vegetables declined substantially

Figure 3: Diet achieved with a decomposition of contribution by scenario component of global change from 2025 to 2050

(A) Ratio of per capita intake to global EL diet recommendations by scenario. Discouraged foods are marked in red and encouraged foods in green. A ratio greater than 1 implies that intake is above the EL recommendation, and a ratio lower than 1 implies that intake is below the EL recommendation. Global EL recommendations (g/capita per day): red meat 14, sugar 31, poultry 42, dairy 250, fruit and vegetables 500, pulses and nuts 75, fish 28. Model regions are grouped by World Bank income classification. All regional aggregates are population weighted averages to account for differences in country size. (B) Contribution of policy bundle components to global change in food intake between 2025 and 2050. The BAU component in panel B includes the impact of changes in population which changes regional weights from 2025 to 2050. The effect of interactions between interventions is computed as the difference between the policy bundle minus the sum over the impacts of each intervention run separately. Impact of interventions by region provided in the appendix (pp 1–2). Source: MAGNET simulations. BAU=business-as-usual. EL=EAT-Lancet. GHG=greenhouse gas. HIC=high-income countries. LMIC=lower middle-income countries. LIC=low-income countries. PB=policy bundle. UMIC=upper-middle-income countries.

(–19 g/capita per day) in the BAU scenario (figure 3B) despite increasing in all but the upper middle-income regions and most so in low-income regions (15 g/capita per day; appendix pp 1–2). Figure 3 presents population-weighted averages. As population growth was highest in low-income regions, their low consumption of fruit and vegetables got a higher weight in 2050, reducing the BAU global average intake. Despite considerable progress, there was a larger number of people substantially under-consuming fruit and vegetables, making it a more pressing concern than in 2025. The PB substantially increased consumption of fruit and vegetables in low-income regions (34 g/capita per day), but the gap

with EL diet recommendations remained the largest of all regions.

The PB had the largest impact on consumption of red meat (pork, beef, and lamb), but consumption remained three times the EL recommendations at global level (figure 3A). NI reduced pork consumption most, while GHG taxes were most effective in reducing the more emission-intensive consumption of beef and lamb (figure 3B). The PB increased the gap with the EL diet recommendation only for dairy in low-income regions, reducing BAU consumption from 88 to 82 g/capita per day (data not shown). Decomposition of the contributions of the interventions showed that GHG taxes and aligning fiscal policies were the main drivers of reduced dairy consumption (figure 3B). With more emission-intensive production, the impact of GHG taxation in low-income countries (–6 g/capita per day; appendix p 2) was stronger than the global average (–4 g/capita per day, figure 3B).

No single intervention shifted all diet components in the desired direction, and effectiveness varied by region. Taxes on agricultural emissions dominated the impact of GHG taxes on food intake, driving 98% or more of the diet shift induced by GHG taxes across regions and food groups. While at global level aligning fiscal policies had minor impact (figure 3B), it increased fish consumption in the high-income region while reducing intake for all other food groups (appendix p 1). This result was mostly driven by removal of agricultural taxes and subsidies in the EU. Although global average impact results suggested that nudging was the most effective intervention, this interpretation did not hold in all regions (appendix pp 1–2). In low-income regions, where consumers are more price-sensitive, GHG taxes and subsidies had the strongest effect across most food groups. Increasing price elasticities and varying the GHG prices in the sensitivity analyses led to minor changes in diets (appendix pp 34–35).

The PB did not restrict total calorie intake, which increased slightly in lower-income regions (18 kcal/day) compared with the BAU (appendix p 3). The EED scenario fixed total calories, addressing concerns for hunger in low-income (199 kcal/day) and lower-middle-income regions (69 kcal/day), while targeting overweight and obesity in upper-middle-income (–101 kcal/day) and high-income regions (–118 kcal/day). Compared with the BAU, consumption shifted towards more processed foods (2–57% increase) and out-of-home consumption (30–74% increase) with the EED. The PB induced only minor changes in shares of processed foods and out-of-home consumption (appendix p 3).

By explicitly targeting GHG, the PB reduced emissions most (–16 GTon CO₂e). Despite not reaching the EL diet recommendation (figure 3A), it reduced primary sector GHG emissions (–4 Gton CO₂e) more than the EED did (–3 Gton CO₂e; figure 4A). GHG taxes in the PB increased costs of fertiliser and other fossil-based inputs. More extensive production and shifts to biobased substitutes for fossils increased total land area (27 million ha; figure 4B)

Figure 4: GHG emissions and agricultural land use compared to the business-as-usual scenario (2050)

(A) Global change in greenhouse gas emissions compared to business as usual. (B) Global change in agricultural land area compared to business as usual. Land use by activities is assigned to categories of use based on material flow balances tracing the use of the produced output. For example, land use for crops is assigned to feed based on the share of livestock sectors in total demand for crops. Source: MAGNET simulations. GHG=greenhouse gas.

which might increase pressure on biodiversity.¹⁸ The use of taxes in the PB increased consumer prices, while exogenously shifting consumption decisions (EED and PB_E) did not limit non-food consumption. As a result, the reduced demand for land by restricting food consumption with the EED (125 million ha) was substantially reduced by increased use of land for non-food (90 million ha) benefiting from lower land prices, and a net contraction

(–35 million ha) remained (figure 4B). Sensitivity analyses showed that a lower GHG price led to a lower reduction in GHG emissions, whereby the impact of land use was also lower, and vice versa with a higher GHG price. Varying GHG taxes by income reduced taxes for emission-intensive production in low-income regions and reduced the agricultural land expansion (appendix pp 36–38). Per-capita GHG emissions remained highly unequal (appendix p 4).

Figure 5: Average household expenditure on food and non-food and minimum cost of the EL diet by scenario and region (2017 PPP US\$/capita per day, 2050)

Sum of the columns is the expenditure-based average household income. A negative value for FE indicates that the minimum cost of the EL diet exceeds the household food expenditures. Household food expenditures with an exogenous shift to the EL diet (EED scenario) are higher than the minimum cost of the EL diet as households' food and non-food preferences are also taken into account in the MAGNET model when exogenously shifting to the EL diet. Model regions are grouped by World Bank income classification. Source: MAGNET simulations. BAU=business as usual. EED=exogenous shift to EL diet. EL=EAT-Lancet. ELM=minimum cost of the EL diet. FE=household food expenditure minus cost of the EL diet. HIC=high-income countries. LIC=low-income countries. LMIC=lower middle-income countries. NF=average household expenditure on non-food. PB=policy bundle. PB_E=exogenous shift to policy bundle diet. PPP=purchasing power parity. Reference=2025 reference year. UMIC=upper middle-income countries.

Emissions in low-income regions were 20% of those in high-income regions in the BAU scenario, further decreasing with the PB (18%) and the EED (15%) scenarios (appendix pp 4,38). The uniform tax on emissions in the PB scenario had substantial justice implications as it increased the costs of less efficient producers disproportionately located in lower income regions, which historically have less access to technology. Compared with the BAU, the PB scenario increased the reliance of low-income regions on imports of animal sourced foods (493% red meat, 33% dairy, and 3% poultry; appendix p 5). The sensitivity analyses showed that only varying the GHG taxes by income level reduced inequality in per-capita GHG emissions, so that in low-income regions they were 25% of those in high-income regions (appendix p 38), against 20% in the BAU (appendix p 4). Varying GHG taxes per capita GDP shifted the burden of GHG reduction to high-income regions with a smaller reduction in global GHG emissions and less agricultural land expansion. Although the total number of workers unable to afford the EL diet decreased in lower income regions, it increased in the upper middle-income regions. It also made the EL diet less affordable with costs exceeding household food expenditures in low-income regions (appendix pp 39–40).

The EED scenario also had justice implications, as it generated reductions of 6–51% in non-primary emissions in the lower income regions (appendix p 4), reflecting a contraction of these non-targeted sectors. To address hunger and malnutrition, EED increased average consumption in lower income regions (appendix p 3), irrespective of the

costs of the diet. As households are bound by their budget constraint (figure 2), they need to reduce non-food demand to accommodate the cost of the exogenously assumed diet. The EED scenario also increased dependency on imports for fruit and vegetables, pulses and nuts, and fish by up to 1747% of BAU levels (appendix p 5).

Affordability of the EL diet for households depends on the cost of the EL diet and household income. Moving from high-income to low-income regions, the cost of the EL diet increased (figure 5). EL diet costs (in 2017 PPP US\$/capita per day) decreased in the BAU from 2025 to 2050 in high-income (2.9–2.5) and upper middle-income regions (3.2–2.8), while costs increased in lower middle-income (4.4–4.5) and low-income regions (4.8–5.2), where high population and income growth outpace productivity improvements. Despite a doubling of average household income in the BAU, the minimum cost of the EL diet exceeded average household food expenditures by 0.5 in low-income countries.

The EED led to a peak in EL diet costs in lower income regions, driven by nearly doubling cost shares of fruit & vegetables and pulses & nuts (appendix p 6). In contrast, subsidies in the PB scenario decreased EL diet costs below 2025 reference levels. The strongest impact was in low-income regions, as emission-intensive primary production generated large GHG tax revenues redistributed as subsidies. Ruminant livestock were most affected. Contraction of emission-intensive food and non-food sectors releases production factors (land, labour, capital) and commodities used as intermediate inputs,

lowering the production costs for other sectors in low-income regions. As a result, even without redistributing tax receipts as subsidies, GHG taxes lowered costs of fruit and vegetables (−5%), pulses and nuts (−5%), fish (−10%), and poultry (−3%) in low-income regions, resulting in the same EL diet costs as in the BAU (appendix p 7). Globally the main driver of increased costs with EED were production limitations increasing average costs of fruit and vegetables (67%) and pulses and nuts (163%), with stronger impacts in low-income regions (148% and 329%).

Affordability decreased when using nudging and information to shift diets: globally costs of the EL diet increased more (2.1%) when shifting to the policy bundle diet (PB_E) and 26.1% with EED than the changes in household income (0% and 0.2%; appendix p 6). These global averages hid stronger impacts in low-income regions, where EL diet costs increased by 3.6% (PB_E) and 34.7% (EED), with household income remaining close to BAU (PB_E) or increasing by 10.1% (EED). Globally, affordability increased with the PB as subsidies lowered the cost of the EL diet (−4.4%) more than it reduced household income (−2.0%). Again, impacts in low-income regions were stronger (−11.1% decrease in cost vs −2.8% decrease in income). Sensitivity analyses showed minimal differences in EL diet affordability when increasing price elasticities or varying GHG prices (appendix pp 39–40).

Average total household income exceeded the minimum cost of the EL diet in all regions and scenarios (figure 5) but missed differences across households. Household heterogeneity could be partly captured in MAGNET by wages of workers. The cost of the EL diet exceeded daily wages for part of the workforce in all regions and scenarios (figure 6A). Affordability of the EL diet for workers was most of a concern in EED, and least when imposing GHG taxes with a redistribution of primary GHG tax revenues. In the remainder, we defined the EL diet as unaffordable if the cost was 50% or more of a daily wage, assuming that about 50% of income is needed for non-food.^{19,20} In the BAU scenario, 24.3% of the workforce (920 million) could not afford the EL diet, rising to 24.8% (940 million) with PB and 27.7% with EED (1048 million; appendix p 8). Geographically, these low-earning workers were mainly located in the two lower-income regions, and in terms of sectors, they were in primary production (figure 6B). Compared with the BAU scenario, the number of workers who could not afford the EL diet increased in encouraged sectors (132.3% with EED, 28.7% with PB) while decreasing in discouraged sectors (−37.7% with EED, −13.3% with PB; appendix p 8). Despite higher wages pulling more workers in encouraged food sectors, the number of workers unable to afford the EL diet thus increased, even when subsidies reduce the cost of the EL diet in the PB. The negative impact of EED on non-food sectors was visible in an increase in workers in manufacturing and services (13.8%) who could not afford the EL diet, while this number slightly decreased with PB (−0.1%; appendix p 8).

Figure 6: Workers unable to afford the EL diet and their location (regions and sectors; 2050)

Not visible in the bar chart are 0.3 million workers in high-income regions where the EL diet costs more than 50% of a daily wage with the policy bundle. Affordability by income group is provided in the appendix p 8. Source: MAGNET simulations. EL=EAT-Lancet. GHG=greenhouse gas.

A shift to a more plant-based diet increases the demand for agricultural labour as crops are more labour-intensive than livestock. Although mostly accommodated by a shift from discouraged to encouraged primary sectors, the number of workers in primary sectors increased compared with the BAU scenario (8% with EED, 1.4% with PB; appendix p 9). This increase in workers in primary sectors drove an increase in the total number of workers unable to afford the EL diet compared with the BAU scenario (13.9% with EED, 2.2% with PB; appendix p 8).

Discussion

We assessed how a policy bundle could shift food production and consumption decisions between 2025 and 2050 towards EL diet recommendations that in empirical⁵ and modelling studies^{2,6,21,22} have been found to yield joint health and environmental benefits. Our economic global CGE model (MAGNET) captures feedback between the food and non-food (including biobased) sectors affecting prices, wages, and income beyond the scope of empirical and agri-food sector analyses.^{2,6,21,22} We compared an exogenous shift to the EL diet, the common approach in existing studies,^{2,6,22} with a bundle of context-specific policy bundle comprising (1) nudging and information based on (scant) empirical evidence, (2) aligning existing fiscal policies with the EL diet, and (3) taxing GHG emissions at a rate compatible with existing policies while simultaneously supporting production of foods that should be consumed more through subsidies. This comparison has, to the best of our knowledge, not been done before and shows that the “how” of a diet shift matters for consumption, environmental and affordability impacts in terms of size and direction of change. With sector wages and employment endogenous, MAGNET provides a dynamic economywide perspective on distributional impacts on workers, to our knowledge not assessed before.

The economywide scope of our global CGE comes with limitations in terms of heterogeneity. Limited detail on processed foods prevents us from capturing shifts to cheaper but less healthy processed foods, for example, in terms of salt or saturated fat content. Despite using highly aggregated food items, our estimate of the minimal cost of the EL diet in 2025 (2.9–4.8 2017 PPP \$) lies within the range of an empirical study of costs of different diets using detailed product data²³ and align with fruit and vegetables accounting for the largest cost share.²⁴ Including only one representative household per model region, our model lacks heterogeneity of within-region household income (eg, rural or urban households) and within-household impacts (eg, differences across age or gender). Our 2025 affordability of the EL diet in terms of average household income falls in the middle of the range found in an empirical study²⁴ for low-income and middle-income regions but may overestimate affordability in high-income regions (appendix pp 19–20). Lacking within-region household heterogeneity, we provide an assessment of affordability of EL diets based on daily wages, which are key for poor workers relying on labour for income.²⁰ We cannot account for non-labour income (which would increase available income), nor the number of dependents per worker (which decreases per capita income). Using 50% of the daily wages as a measure of affordability aligns with earlier studies^{19,20} and brings our 2025 reference year global estimates (38% of workers unable to afford the EL diet) close to a household income based assessment³ (44% of people unable to afford a healthy diet). The CGE model has been calibrated to empirical data that might not capture consumer or producer responses to fundamental changes

in the food system. Potential breaks with current observed behaviour warrant future research as economywide feedback will be complex, leaving the net impact undetermined (appendix p 20).

Despite reducing overconsumption and underconsumption for most food groups, a large gap remains between EL diet recommendations and consumption changes achieved through the policy bundle. Shifting consumption with nudging and information is often preferred to price incentives or regulation as being less restrictive. Although effective for the limited number of targeted foods, our quantification builds on scant empirical evidence, making the assumed diet shift optimistic. Information, however, could support a diet shift indirectly by raising awareness, which increases public acceptability and thus the political feasibility of price interventions.^{25–27} Nudging and information do not provide a mechanism to compensate for the higher cost of the EL diet. As in other modelling studies,^{2,6,22} the EED scenario assumes a full shift irrespective of its costs for consumers. This demand shift is not only beyond the range found empirically,⁷ rising prices are also likely to limit the effectiveness of nudging and information. Especially in low-income regions where households need to halve BAU non-food expenditures to stay within their budget, a shift to the EL diet based on nudging and information seems implausible.

Aligning fiscal policies, removing producer and consumer subsidies on foods to be consumed less, or removing producer and consumer taxes on foods to be consumed more, had substantial impact, and in the desired direction, in high-income regions with higher current levels of intervention. Taxing GHG emissions was more effective than nudging to reduce ruminant-based consumption (beef and lamb, dairy), but less effective for pork. A uniform GHG tax had a stronger impact in lower-income regions with emission-intensive production, in line with findings from an agricultural sector model.²¹ Additional taxes based on impacts not accounted for in markets, like health damage, could be considered to further reduce red meat consumption. To limit negative income effects GHG tax revenues could be used to support producers in reducing their emission intensity. For simplicity, the policy bundle provided output subsidies to encouraged food sectors, not steering production adjustments in a specific direction. Alternative subsidy schemes targeting specific inputs could be explored, for example aiming to further reduce emissions or increase wages.

Production and consumption adjustments limit environmental gains of all diet changes compared with agriculture-focused analyses, but feedback and outcomes depend on whether a diet shift is assumed exogenous or achieved through the policy bundle. The importance of economywide feedback is illustrated by contrasting the increase in cropland due to non-food demand under the exogenous EL diet, with a study using an agricultural sector model finding a reduction in cropland.¹ The decrease in GHG emissions under the exogenous EL diet contrasts

with an increase driven by non-primary sectors found in an earlier MAGNET study.³ The difference is due to quantifying the EL diet using a higher resolution in food commodities and more detailed data on intake, diets, and regional energy requirements. The net impact is visible in a limited calorie intake reduction, contrasting with reductions up to 24% in the earlier study. A second reason is additional detail on non-food biomass sectors facilitating a shift from fossils to renewable resources in the current study.

The impact of joint price and income changes through economywide feedback is missing from previous assessments of the affordability of healthy diets.^{23,24} Despite lowering household income, the EL diet became more affordable for households with the policy bundle subsidising encouraged food, in line with earlier studies not accounting for the income effect.²¹ The number of workers unable to afford the EL diet increased in all scenarios, as a more plant-based diet breaks with the historical trend of structural transformation from agriculture to better paid manufacturing and services jobs. The exogenous EL diet shift also increased the number of workers in manufacturing and services unable to afford the EL diet due to negative impacts on non-food sectors (negative income effect) on top of higher EL diet cost (negative price effect). Subsidies of encouraged sectors in the policy bundle avoid this negative impact on non-food workers. These results show the importance to account for heterogeneous income changes and looking beyond the food sectors when analysing a large diet shift.

Expanding supply of fruit and vegetables and of pulses and nuts by increasing productivity and reducing food loss and waste²⁸ is needed to limit the rising cost when shifting to a more plant-based diet. Soaring prices might stimulate investments in these sectors, while GHG taxes will stimulate investments to reduce climate impacts of food and non-food production. How a productivity change is achieved, including the way in which investments are financed, determines the economywide feedback loops driving environmental and affordability impacts. The policy bundle induces an extensification of crop production as GHG taxes increase the cost of fertiliser. If the subsidies were financed by an output tax on discouraged foods, fertiliser use would not be discouraged. Similar to the diet shift explored in this study, the scope and impact of a productivity increase might be altered when making interventions and investments explicit and should be explored in future work.

In line with existing studies,^{29,30} price increases are moderated by increased imports, but the pattern depends on how diets are changed: fruit, vegetables, pulses and nuts with an exogenous EL diet, animal sourced foods with the policy bundle. International trade is a dual-edge sword, also making discouraged foods more affordable,^{29,30} and reflects past lack of access to food and non-food technologies in lower income regions thus perpetuating inequalities. Future studies could explore the role of international trade to improve EL diet affordability for countries facing

biophysical limitations, which cannot be addressed by closing yield gaps, or preferring investments in non-agricultural sectors to boost wage income.

While already providing a complex analysis, the policy bundle in this study has a limited scope focused on existing policies and global support for reducing GHG emissions expressed by the Paris climate agreement. We did not explore regulation of production that might be needed to limit agricultural land expansion or an increasing intake of ultra-processed foods and other discouraged food items. Aligning public procurement of foods with the EL diet recommendations and regulating the food environment in and around schools can improve the diet of children and other subgroups in the population. The increasing number of workers unable to afford the EL diet indicates a potential need to regulate the labour market, for example with minimum wages. Else the majority of those producing encouraged foods might remain unable to afford the EL diet themselves, even when productivity gains are achieved. Income tax schemes might also be shifted from taxing labour to taxing capital and/or natural resource use to increase wage income and reduce environmental impacts.

Reducing subsidies and introducing taxes will generate opposition by affected producers and consumers, which might limit the scope for the policies explored in this study. Riots have occurred in high-income regions when reforming European agricultural policy and in low-income countries when removing subsidies on staple foods or fuel. Less public opposition can be expected from sector lobby groups.³¹ Country-specific policy bundles will need to be crafted, balancing effectiveness and political feasibility³² while acknowledging that food consumption is determined by more than affordability and nutritional needs. In high-income countries, EL diets cost a fraction of current food expenditures, and the majority of households can easily afford the EL diet but choose not to. Our study takes into account consumer preferences for specific commodities, as shown by food expenditures exceeding the minimum cost of the EL diet when exogenously shifting to the EL diet. It unfortunately does not provide guidance on what drives these preferences and how to influence them, nor does the existing literature. Reaping the potential health and environmental benefits from a full global shift in a just manner requires creative thinking on new interventions and sustained collective action to fundamentally change our food system.

Contributors

MK and TdL are equal co-first authors. MK and TdL co-designed the study. MK, TdL, and W-JvZ quantified the model scenarios. MK and TdL ran the model scenarios, analysed the results, and wrote the original draft. MK acquired the project funding and led the project. All authors had access to the data, commented on and interpreted the results. MK, TdL, and WvZ have verified the underlying data. All authors contributed to review and editing and were responsible for the decision to submit the manuscript.

Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests.

Data sharing

Access to model code and data provided upon request and is bound by licence agreements.

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